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OPEN ACCESS

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ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

Scientific publications associated with the ARIES project are stored in the **CDS database**. These publications include: *journal publications, conference/workshop papers, scientific/technical notes, academic dissertations, posters, presentations and handouts, press articles.*

- All **ARIES publications** (including Transnational Access) must include the following acknowledgement:

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